

Meta-Analysis of Anabolic-Androgenic Steroids(AAS): A Comprehensive Review of Their Physiological, Psychological, And Performance Effects

Matthew Goodson

Anabolic-Androgenic Steroids(AAS) are a synthetic class of testosterone. Evidence from recent studies highlight the increased use of AAS for reasons not medically prescribed. AAS can be appealing due to the exogenous use of supraphysiological doses of AAS being widely reported to increase libido, muscle mass, endurance, and decrease recovery time. This can be seen as a “miracle” for those looking to achieve a certain physique. This has led to a significant increase in the use of AAS. By examining and synthesizing existing research, this meta-analysis aims to investigate the physiological, psychological, and performance effects of Anabolic-Androgenic Steroid (AAS) use and its implications for individuals and compile the information in such a way that the effects of AAS can be clearly understood by the reader.

Keywords: Anabolic-androgenic steroids, performance enhancing drugs, testosterone, protein synthesis, metabolism, physiology

In 1993 it was estimated in a study in the National Library of Medicine that more than one million people who currently or have previously abused AAS. According to the same study, approximately 0.9% of men and 0.1% of women have or currently use AAS¹. A more recent study published in The American Journal of Addictions in September of 2013 indicates a nearly three to four fold increase in the use of AAS. Estimating 2.9-4 million people in the United states having used or currently using AAS². The increasing popularity of AAS use can be attributed to various factors, including the desire for improved athletic performance, increased muscle mass, enhanced physical appearance, and a perceived shortcut to achieving fitness goals. This is indicated by a study in the British Journal of Sports Medicine that indicated nearly two-thirds of people who use AAS do not compete at an amateur or professional level³, underscoring the broad appeal and diverse demographic encompassed by AAS users. That is not to say that these individuals do not have a legitimate medical

reason for using AAS. It is becoming increasingly common for doctors to prescribe synthetic hormones, such as an estered testosterone, to address specific needs including hypogonadism⁴. However, having medical use alone does not mean that there are no inherent risks. The misuse and abuse of AAS, even under medical supervision, can have a plethora of risks that can be more or less dangerous depending on dosage, current health, and genetics. These adverse reactions can include cardiovascular issues, neurotoxicity, gynecomastia, hypogonadism, and hypo/hyper manic episodes (often referred to as Roid Rage)⁵⁶⁷⁸.

This paper aims to provide a comprehensive examination of the physiological, psychological, and performance effects of AAS use through a meta-analysis of existing literature. By synthesizing and critically evaluating relevant studies, this research seeks to enhance understanding of the multifaceted implications of AAS use and contribute to informed decision-making in both clinical and non-clinical contexts. In the subsequent sections, we will

explore the specific physiological mechanisms underlying AAS effects, examine the psychological implications, evaluate the impact on athletic performance, and discuss the potential risks and adverse effects associated with AAS use.

The subsequent sections will discuss the specific findings and implications of this meta-analysis.

Mechanism of Action:

The anabolic, or muscle building effects, of AAS is determined by the intramuscular androgen receptors. When these receptors are triggered within muscle cells it activates transcription genes that begin or accelerate protein synthesis. AAS also have the ability to increase the number of androgen receptors in the body⁹. It is also reported in a study published to Science Direct in 2011 that heavy resistance training can lead to an increase in androgen receptors throughout the body¹⁰. This could indicate an additional complementary relationship between resistance exercise and the use of AAS.

Protein Synthesis:

Further research suggests additional metabolic and psychological effects. It is reported that the anabolic effects of steroids can affect our metabolism by triggering the increase of protein synthesis¹¹. This allows dietary proteins to be metabolized and used for the development and repair of muscle fibers more effectively than someone who does not use AAS. The protein synthesis is triggered due to the anabolic effect on the muscle cells to multinucleate. This occurs as two muscle cells merge into one allowing the multiple nuclei to share the load of the major cellular function like growth and cell division. There is also evidence of additional benefit of resistance exercise being an increase in cells with multiple nuclei¹².

Modulation of Androgen Receptors:

Testosterone is the primary molecule that will bind to androgen receptors (AR). Androgen receptors are what modulate gene expression with regards to steroid binding¹³. In simple terms this means testosterone “targets” the androgen receptors and once it reaches the receptor it “turns on” the genes for muscle growth and development. Once affecting the targeted cells testosterone undergoes an irreversible reduction into 5 α -dihydrotestosterone (DHT) via the enzyme 5 α -reductase. This reaction furthers the effect as DHT has a greater ability to bind to androgen receptors than testosterone¹⁴. When the testosterone has bonded to the androgen receptors it is shown to accelerate AR response to acute resistance training. This also has the benefit of preventing catabolism¹⁵. It can further prevent catabolism and muscle atrophy through the way AAS and glucocorticoids interact. While it is not known exactly what mechanism they interact through, studies have found that the muscle atrophy effect of glucocorticoid treatment can be prevented through the administration of AAS alongside exercise¹⁶.

Muscle Growth:

The leading hypothesis as to how testosterone and its synthetic derivative increase muscle growth is that the steroids promote a special kind of stem cell, called mesenchymal pluripotent cells into choosing to become a muscular skeletal cell. AAS also are able to prevent the growth of new fat cells (adipogenesis) by modulating an androgen controlled pathway¹⁷.

Additional studies have suggested other effects of AAS that could contribute to increased muscle growth. After binding to the androgen receptors, the testosterone complex is able to bind to DNA activating many gene expressions. This includes creating an environment with a surplus of nitrogen¹⁸. This nitrogen is important for cells to be able to convert amino acids into proteins¹⁹.

Further research emphasizes the importance of satellite cells and muscle growth. A satellite cell is a muscular stem cell. It is believed that these satellite cells are responsible for muscle growth and repair during and after hypertrophy²⁰. Studies have shown that those who are administered AAS have slightly higher satellite cell production than those who do not use AAS. The same study did find that the number of fibers with myonuclei was notably higher in AAS users. (4.8 ± 1.2 in Type I and 5.7 ± 1.4 in Type II fibers in AAS users and 3.9 ± 1.1 in Type I and 5 ± 1.7 in Type II in the non-AAS using group)²¹.

Psychological Effect:

Studies also show a wide and complex range of psychological and emotional effects of steroids, both positive and negative including increased alertness, elevated mood, and increased sexual libido. The negative effects could include increased aggression, irritability, and “negative outlook”^{22 23}. It should be noted that many of the studies relating to psychology and mood while using AAS are generally conducted using a survey with primary focus on negative feelings. Further in depth research should be done to ascertain a full psychological view of the use of AAS. It is believed that supraphysiological doses of testosterone or AAS reduces the connectivity of the right dorsolateral prefrontal cortex (DLPFC) and the right amygdala, which is considered the emotion-regulation system. This essentially means the elevation or depression in mood is likely caused by a loss of neuro-connectors in the part of the brain that regulates emotions²⁴.

Table 1. Commonly used anabolic steroids.

17 α alkyl derivatives Oral agents	17 β -ester derivatives Injectable agents
Methandrostenolone	Testosterone esters: cypionate, enanthate, heptylate, propionate
Methyltestosterone	Nandrolone esters
Oxandrolone	Boldenone
Oxymetholone	Methenolone
Stanozolol	Trenbolone
Ethylestrenol	Dromostanolone
Danazol	
Fluoxymesterone	

Physiology:

Testosterone is the primary identifying male sex hormone that is produced in the testes. This is the primary hormone that leads young men into puberty. It also plays a primary function in the regulation of protein synthesis, sexual function, and plasma lipid regulation. Natural testosterone is considered to have an anabolic:androgenic rating of 100:100²⁵. On average, healthy men will range between 300-1000 ng/dl of total testosterone. It is important to note that total testosterone does not present a full physiologic view of an individual as free testosterone is the only physiologically active form of testosterone and composes approximately 1-2% of the total serum testosterone²⁶. A majority of testosterone found in the body is bound to Sex Hormone Binding Globulin(SHBG) or weakly bound to albumin. The remaining, unbound, testosterone is what is considered Free Testosterone(FT). The importance of FT is explained through the Free Hormone Hypothesis. Simply stated, it is suggested that free and albumin bound forms of

testosterone are more available to diffuse out of capillaries and into cells triggering the appropriate anabolic-androgenic response²⁷. AAS are known to increase both total serum testosterone and free testosterone²⁸. Anabolic-androgenic steroids are synthetic derivatives of natural testosterone designed with the specific intention to maximize the muscle building and lipolytic (anabolic) properties and minimize the masculating (androgenic) effects such as hair growth and acne²⁹. Testosterone can be synthesized in various ways to alter administration methods. These include intramuscular injections, topical gels or patches, and oral administration methods³⁰. The use of AAS is also known to have significant effects on the rest of the endocrine system. One study on the hormonal effects of anabolic steroids found significant decreases in thyroid stimulating hormone, thyroxine, triiodothyronine, free thyroxine, and thyroid hormone-binding globulin (TBG), luteinizing hormone, and follicle stimulating hormone resulting in a reduction in testosterone being produced in the testes. The study also found growth hormone levels had increased up to 60 times original levels as well as an increase in estrogen levels attributed to the higher levels of testosterone being aromatized into estrogen³¹. It is also shown that anabolic steroids can have a negative effect on cholesterol. One study found a significant decrease in HDL cholesterol, 29 ± 8 mg/dL compared to 61 ± 14 mg/dL in non users. The study also noted the mean levels of LDL cholesterol was higher in the users of AAS. 150 ± 44 mg/dL vs 125 ± 38 mg/dL in non users³². These dramatic changes can pose a health risk depending on overall health and genetics. AAS are further known to increase blood haematocrit, the percentage by volume of red blood cells in blood. Research has found that users of AAS had their blood haematocrit increase by 9.6%³³. This is an often overlooked but very significant side effect of steroid use.

Red blood cells are the primary vessel for delivering oxygen throughout the body, including muscle cells³⁴. Higher oxygen saturation or oxygen carrying ability would allow the muscles to fatigue slower and allow for further hypertrophy.

AAS also have a significant effect on various organs. Including the liver, heart, kidneys, and skin.

Liver:

The liver is the primary organ that works to clear steroids from the body which has led to concerns of the potential hepatotoxicity of continuous AAS use. Oral anabolic steroids are responsible for the majority of liver related injuries attributed to AAS. These include acute cholestatic syndrome, enzyme elevations, chronic vascular injury to the liver, and hepatic tumors. However it is noted that esterated derivatives of testosterone seem to have fewer effects on the liver and that the effects on the liver seem to be reversible after discontinuation³⁵.

Heart:

It is well documented that AAS have a negative impact on the heart. The heart is a muscle, different than skeletal muscle but still able to be affected by AAS. This can lead to significant risks including high blood pressure, myocardial ischemia, reshaping of the ventricles, and even sudden cardiac death. It is also reported that these effects have long lasting implications on the heart³⁶.

Kidneys:

Damage to the kidneys is not as widely reported as the previous organs; however there are limited studies that have found acute renal failure associated with AAS abuse. There are even more isolated incidents that report Wilms' tumors as a result of using AAS³⁷. More research is needed to have a comprehensive understanding.

Skin:

One of the most widely reported side effects of AAS use is an increase in acne. Abusing AAS can induce cystic acne (acne conglobata) and hemorrhagic acne (acne fulminans)³⁸. However, due to the same mechanism of freeing more skin-surface lipids allowing more cholesterol and fatty acids to make it to the surface of the skin. This can lead to oily skin, sebaceous cysts, androgenic alopecia, and more that are less often reported³⁹.

Psychology:

It is not uncommon to hear of psychological changes happening during AAS use. The media often portrays steroids as almost guaranteed to cause “roid-rage”. It is true that there are numerous psychological effects of anabolic steroids but as it was pointed out in a 2011 study by Mario J. Vassallo and Tracy W. Olich, the psychological effects are often inaccurate and based on speculation alone. Their study found that nearly 95% of their participants experienced heightened mood and increased self-confidence⁴⁰. Of course the criticism of steroids and the psychological effects do have merit. A study conducted in 2020 found that nearly one third of those who use AAS develop an addiction or dependency to steroids. Further, this dependency is characterized by an increase in psychopathy, anti-social and aggressive behaviors, and cognitive impairment⁴¹. There is also evidence that in some cases psychosis and thoughts of suicide can occur⁴².

A study on anabolic use in adolescents also found that those who used AAS had a better view of their own bodies⁴³. A similarly sized study on the mood of current and previous adult AAS users found significant elevations in enthusiasm, libido, and body image. It goes further to explain that across all subjects there was no significant difference in any Profile of Moods factor, total mood disturbance, total

Buss-Durkee Hostility Inventory score, or any subscale. They do note that there was a self reported increase in aggression, irritability, and changes in insomnia amongst users⁴⁴.

Studies have also found addictive properties of high dose, continued use of AAS. Symptoms can include preoccupation or obsession with the drug and use of it, ignoring or downplaying side effects, drug cravings, and difficulty stopping⁴⁵. It has been noted that health consequences and side effects of long term abuse are reversible after discontinuing the use of AAS. It is important to note that despite this serious, life-threatening events have been attributed to the abuse of AAS⁴⁶. Similarly to many drugs, stopping AAS does have withdrawal symptoms. The self reported withdrawal symptoms can include: extended periods of depression, loss of libido, lethargy, AAS craving, and in some cases reports of anorexia and bulimia. It should be noted that these symptoms are often the opposite effects of what AAS use has.

It is currently believed that the mechanism by which AAS dependency is formed is through reinforcement due to the muscle growth effects. This is different from many other drugs such as cocaine or heroin which activate the reward mechanisms of the brain almost instantly^{47 48}. This difference can be explained through the fact that the primary reason individuals use AAS is to enhance their physical appearance⁴⁹. The rapid changes that AAS can achieve would also stimulate the reward mechanisms of the brain leading to addiction and dependency.

A significant amount of the psychological effects can be traced to a single mechanism of testosterone and its derivatives. This is the ability to disrupt and suppress the hypothalamic pituitary gonadal axis which regulates the production and secretion of growth hormone (GH), thyroid-stimulating hormone (TSH), follicle-stimulating hormone (FSH), luteinizing hormone (LH), prolactin and adrenocorticotropic hormone (ACTH)⁵⁰. A study found in body

builders who regularly abused AAS had a noted significant decrease in TSH which regulates the production of thyroid hormone⁵¹, LH which regulates the production of natural testosterone in the testes⁵², and inhibin B which is responsible for the secretion of follicle stimulating hormone⁵³ which in turn is responsible for stimulating sperm growth and development⁵⁴. However, the same study did detect an increase in prolactin which develops mammary tissue⁵⁵, IGF-1 which manages the production and secretion of GH⁵⁶, and Thyroxine (T4) which significantly contributes to metabolism regulation and muscle control⁵⁷.

Performance Enhancing Ability:

The primary reason behind AAS use is the performance enhancing ability of the substances. Through their ability to directly increase the number of androgen receptors⁵⁸, decreasing adipose tissue, and faster recovery time, which lead to an increase in lean body mass and a decrease in fat⁵⁹.

Muscle Mass and Strength:

FGF2 and the FGF receptor are critical for skeletal muscle growth and development for their role in signaling satellite cells to perform terminal differentiation and become muscle cells⁶⁰. While the effects of how testosterone or AAS affects FGF2 and the FGF receptors it has been studied to show that those given AAS as a treatment for hypogonadism that Plasma FGF2 and IGF-1 concentrations increased after they were treated using the AAS. Showing a correlation between testosterone levels and FGF2 and IGF-1 levels which would lead to increased muscle growth⁶¹.

Numerous studies have found a direct relationship with the administration of AAS and an increase in muscle mass. One found that one group on 600 mg testosterone enanthate per week for 10 weeks. This group noticed a fivefold increase in their total and free

testosterone levels. The groups also had a 3 day per week resistance training routine. Compared to the control group, the group receiving weekly AAS injections had larger increases in arm and leg muscle growth. In some cases 12% greater increase in size over the same amount of time compared to the control group. There were also noted significant strength gains compared to the control group. The study specifically measured bench press and squatting. In the AAS group they saw an 11% strength increase over the control group and a 16% increase for the squat exercise endurance⁶².

One of testosterone's functions is to regulate prostatic steroid binding protein. It achieves this by stimulating the accumulation of mRNA. With greater amounts of testosterone, more mRNA will be triggered to be made and accumulated⁶³. And one study on anabolic effects on growth and protein metabolism and found increased body and skeletal growth as well as an increase in muscle protein synthesis. The study attributed these effects of the AAS to increased RNA concentration⁶⁴.

AAS also has an interesting relationship with resistance training. The ultimate goal of resistance training is hypertrophy, where the muscle fibers tear and allow satellite cells to enter and form new myonuclei⁶⁵. This is important because testosterone also indirectly signals satellite cells to become muscle cells through FGF2.

Another important function of AAS is the prevention of catabolism, where muscle cells begin to be broken down by the body. There are studies that show promise for using the AAS oxandrolone (Anavar) as a way to prevent catabolism induced by severe burns. The patients receiving the Anavar treatment regained lean body mass two to three times faster than the control group. The treatment was discontinued after the return of 80% of the lost body weight. After 6 months the patients were measured again and found the Anavar group had maintained

their body mass whereas the control group still had yet to recover the full mass⁶⁶. The combined anabolic effects of AAS allowed recovering patients to recover mass faster, fuller, and maintain it after discontinuing treatment.

Endurance:

While there is no clear and direct evidence linking the use of AAS to increased endurance, many of the anabolic effects are reported to enhance endurance. As stated, a supraphysiological dose of testosterone is known to increase red blood cell count⁶⁷. The primary function of red blood cells is to carry the gasses, such as oxygen we inhale from our lungs and to our cells and carry away waste such as carbon dioxide away from cells and to our lungs⁶⁸. Having more available oxygen means cells can better respire, remove waste, and increase overall endurance.

Recovery:

It has been shown in numerous studies that AAS have the ability to aid in healing muscles, tendons and ligaments after exercise and injury. One study found that AAS contributes to the repair of ligaments and tendons through FGF2. FGF2 plays a critical role in angiogenesis and mitogenesis and facilitates collagen synthesis which is important for repairing ligaments and tendons⁶⁹.

Conclusion:

This meta-analysis has analyzed and compiled a comprehensive assessment of the physiological, psychological, and performance implications of anabolic-androgenic steroids. By reviewing the available literature we have acquired valuable insights into the multi-faceted effects, both positive and negative, of AAS usage. This includes clinical and non-clinical settings. With the continuing rise in the use of AAS it is important to have access to a comprehensive compilation of information to be as informed as possible. The goal of the paper was to provide

this information in an understandable, digestible, but still thorough manner.

References:

1. Yesalis CE, Kennedy NJ, Kopstein AN, Bahrke MS. Anabolic-androgenic steroid use in the United States. *JAMA*. 1993 Sep 8;270(10):1217-21. PMID: 8355384.
2. Pope, H.G., Jr., Kanayama, G., Athey, A., Ryan, E., Hudson, J.I. and Baggish, A. (2014), The lifetime prevalence of anabolic-androgenic steroid use and dependence in Americans: Current best estimates. *Am J Addict*, 23: 371-377.
3. Evans NAGym and tonic: a profile of 100 male steroid users. *British Journal of Sports Medicine* 1997;31:54-58
4. Barbonetti, A, D'Andrea, S, Francavilla, S. Testosterone replacement therapy. *Andrology*. 2020; 8: 1551– 1566.
5. Gen Kanayama, James I. Hudson, Harrison G. Pope, Illicit anabolic-androgenic steroid use, *Hormones and Behavior*, Volume 58, Issue 1, 2010, Pages 111-121, ISSN 0018-506X,
6. Pomara, C., Neri, M., Bello, S., Fiore, C., Riezzo, I., & Turillazzi, E. (1970, January 1). Neurotoxicity by synthetic androgen steroids: Oxidative stress, apoptosis, and Neuropathology: A Review. Latest TOC RSS.
7. Fnu Deepinder & Glenn D Braunstein (2012) Drug-induced gynecomastia: an evidence-based review, *Expert Opinion on Drug Safety*, 11:5, 779-795
8. Cyrus D. Rahnema, Larry I. Lipshultz, Lindsey E. Crosnoe, Jason R. Kovac, Edward D. Kim, Anabolic steroid-induced hypogonadism: diagnosis and treatment, *Fertility and Sterility*, Volume 101, Issue 5, 2014, Pages 1271-1279, ISSN 0015-0282,
9. Ganesan K, Rahman S, Zito PM. Anabolic Steroids. In: *StatPearls*. StatPearls Publishing, Treasure Island (FL); 2022. PMID: 29494025.
10. Juha P. Ahtiainen, Juha J. Hulmi, William J. Kraemer, Maarit Lehti, Kai Nyman, Harri Selänne, Markku Alen, Arto Pakarinen, Jyrki Komulainen, Vuokko Kovanen, Antti A. Mero, Keijo Häkkinen, Heavy resistance exercise training and skeletal muscle androgen receptor expression in younger and older men, *Steroids*, Volume 76, Issues 1–2, 2011, Pages 183-192, ISSN 0039-128X,
11. Melinda Sheffield-Moore (2000) Androgens and the control of skeletal muscle protein synthesis, *Annals of Medicine*, 32:3, 181-186,
12. Anabolic steroids increase exercise tolerance Tetsuro Tamaki, Shuichi Uchiyama, Yoshiyasu Uchiyama, Akira Akatsuka, Roland R. Roy, and V. Reggie Edgerton *American Journal of Physiology-Endocrinology and Metabolism* 2001 280:6, E973-E981
13. Faisal Rahman, Helen C. Christian, Non-classical actions of testosterone: an update, *Trends in Endocrinology & Metabolism*, Volume 18, Issue 10, 2007, Pages 371-378, ISSN 1043-2760,
14. Kicman, A.T. (2008), Pharmacology of anabolic steroids. *British Journal of Pharmacology*, 154: 502-521.
15. Barry A. Spiering, William J. Kraemer, Jakob L. Vingren, Nicholas A. Ratamess, Jeffrey M. Anderson, Lawrence E. Armstrong, Bradley C. Nindl, Jeff S. Volek, Keijo Häkkinen, Carl M. Maresh, Elevated endogenous testosterone concentrations potentiate muscle androgen receptor responses to resistance exercise, *The Journal of Steroid Biochemistry and Molecular Biology*, Volume 114, Issues 3–5, 2009, Pages 195-199, ISSN 0960-0760,
16. Hickson RC, Czerwinski SM, Falduto MT, Young AP. Glucocorticoid antagonism by exercise and androgenic-anabolic steroids. *Medicine and Science in Sports and Exercise*. 1990 Jun;22(3):331-340. PMID: 2199753.
17. Herbst, Karen L; Bhasin, Shalender. Testosterone action on skeletal muscle. *Current Opinion in Clinical Nutrition and Metabolic Care* 7(3):p 271-277, May 2004.
18. Hall, R. C., & Hall, R. C. (2005). Abuse of supraphysiologic doses of anabolic steroids. *Southern medical journal*, 98(5), 550-555.
19. Hammarqvist, F., Strömberg, C., von der Decken, A., Vinnars, E., & Wernerman, J. (1992). Biosynthetic human growth hormone preserves both muscle protein synthesis and the decrease in muscle-free glutamine, and improves whole-body nitrogen economy after operation. *Annals of surgery*, 216(2), 184–191
20. Blaauw, B., Reggiani, C. The role of satellite cells in muscle hypertrophy. *J Muscle Res Cell Motil* 35, 3–10 (2014).
21. KADI, FAWZI; ERIKSSON, ANDERS; HOLMNER, STAFFAN; THORNELL, LARS-ERIC. Effects of anabolic steroids on the muscle cells of strength-trained athletes. *Medicine & Science in Sports & Exercise* 31(11):p 1528, November 1999.
22. Bahrke, M. S. (2007). Psychological effects of endogenous testosterone and anabolic-androgenic steroids. In D. Smith & M. Bar-Eli (Eds.), *Essential readings in sport and exercise psychology* (pp. 356–371). Human Kinetics.
23. Parrott AC, Choi PY, Davies M. J. *Sports Med. Phys. Fitness* 1994; 34(3): 292-298.
24. Votinov, M., Wagels, L., Hoffstaedter, F. et al. Effects of exogenous testosterone application on network connectivity within emotion regulation systems. *Sci Rep* 10, 2352 (2020).
25. Kam, P.C.A. and Yarrow, M. (2005), Anabolic steroid abuse: physiological and anaesthetic considerations. *Anaesthesia*, 60: 685-692.
26. Justin M. Johnson, Lisa B. Nachtigall, Theodore A. Stern, The Effect of Testosterone Levels on Mood in Men: A Review, *Psychosomatics*, Volume 54, Issue 6, 2013, Pages 509-514, ISSN 0033-3182
27. RT Journal Article A1 Mendel, Carl M. T1 The Free Hormone Hypothesis: A Physiologically Based Mathematical Model* *JF Endocrine Reviews JO Endocr Rev YR* 1989
28. Creutzberg, Eva C.; Schols, Annemie M.W.J.. Anabolic steroids. *Current Opinion in Clinical Nutrition and Metabolic Care* 2(3):p 243-253, May 1999.
29. Haupt, H. A., & Rovere, G. D. (1984). Anabolic steroids: a review of the literature. *The American journal of sports medicine*, 12(6), 469–484.
30. Nackeeran, Sirpi*; Kohn, Taylor; Gonzalez, Daniel; White, Joshua; Ory, Jesse; Ramasamy, Ranjith The Effect of Route of Testosterone on Changes in Hematocrit: A Systematic Review and Bayesian

- Network Meta-Analysis of Randomized Trials, *Journal of Urology*: January 2022 - Volume 207 - Issue 1 - p 1-252
31. Alen M, Rahkila P, Reinilä M, Vihko R. Androgenic-anabolic steroid effects on serum thyroid, pituitary and steroid hormones in athletes. *The American Journal of Sports Medicine*. 1987;15(4):357-361.
 32. O.Lynn Webb, Peter M. Laskarzewski, Charles J. Glueck, Severe depression of high-density lipoprotein cholesterol levels in weight lifters and body builders by self-administered exogenous testosterone and anabolic-androgenic steroids, *Metabolism*, Volume 33, Issue 11, 1984, Pages 971-975, ISSN 0026-0495
 33. Alén M Androgenic steroid effects on liver and red cells. *British Journal of Sports Medicine* 1985;19:15-20.
 34. Naotaka Hamasaki, Masaaki Yamamoto; Red Blood Cell Function and Blood Storage. *Vox Sanguinis* 1 December 2000; 79 (4): 191–197.
 35. Niedfeldt, Mark W. MD. Anabolic Steroid Effect on the Liver. *Current Sports Medicine Reports* 17(3):p 97-102, March 2018.
 36. Mack Lee Sullivan, Charles M. Martinez, Paul Gennis, E. John Gallagher, The cardiac toxicity of anabolic steroids, *Progress in Cardiovascular Diseases*, Volume 41, Issue 1, 1998, Pages 1-15
 37. Modlinski, R., Fields, K.B. The effect of anabolic steroids on the gastrointestinal system, kidneys, and adrenal glands. *Curr Sports Med Rep* 5, 104–109 (2006).
 38. Melnik, B., Jansen, T., & Grabbe, S. (2007). Abuse of anabolic-androgenic steroids and bodybuilding acne: an underestimated health problem. *Journal der Deutschen Dermatologischen Gesellschaft = Journal of the German Society of Dermatology : JDDG*, 5(2), 110–117.
 39. Scott, M. J., 3rd, & Scott, A. M. (1992). Effects of anabolic-androgenic steroids on the pilosebaceous unit. *Cutis*, 50(2), 113–116.
 40. Mario J. Vassallo & Tracy W. Olrich (2010) Confidence by injection: Male users of anabolic steroids speak of increases in perceived confidence through anabolic steroid use, *International Journal of Sport and Exercise Psychology*, 8:1, 70-80
 41. Vaskinn, A., Hauger, L.E. & Bjørnebekk, A. Theory of mind in users of anabolic androgenic steroids. *Psychopharmacology* 237, 3191–3199 (2020).
 42. Trenton, A.J., Currier, G.W. Behavioural Manifestations of Anabolic Steroid Use. *CNS Drugs* 19, 571–595 (2005).
 43. Komoroski EM, Rickert VI. Adolescent Body Image and Attitudes to Anabolic Steroid Use. *Am J Dis Child*. 1992;146(7):823–828.
 44. Bahrke MS, Wright JE, Strauss RH, Catlin DH. Psychological moods and subjectively perceived behavioral and somatic changes accompanying anabolic-androgenic steroid use. *The American Journal of Sports Medicine*. 1992;20(6):717-724.
 45. Kashkin KB, Kleber HD. Hooked on Hormones? An Anabolic Steroid Addiction Hypothesis. *JAMA*. 1989;262(22):3166–3170.
 46. Kirk J. Brower (1992) Anabolic Steroids: Addictive, Psychiatric, and Medical Consequences, *American Journal on Addictions*, 1:2, 100-114
 47. William A. Carlezon et al. ,Regulation of Cocaine Reward by CREB. *Science* 282,2272-2275(1998).
 48. Spyraiki, C., Fibiger, H.C. & Phillips, A.G. Attenuation of heroin reward in rats by disruption of the mesolimbic dopamine system. *Psychopharmacology* 79, 278–283 (1983).
 49. Brower, K. J. (2002). Anabolic steroid abuse and dependence. *Current Psychiatry Reports*, 4(5), 377–387.
 50. Sheng Julietta A., Bales Natalie J., Myers Sage A., Bautista Anna I., Roueinfar Mina, Hale Taben M., Handa Robert J. The Hypothalamic-Pituitary-Adrenal Axis: Development, Programming Actions of Hormones, and Maternal-Fetal Interactions. *Frontiers in Behavioral Neuroscience* Volume 14, 2021 ISSN: 1662-5153
 51. U.S. National Library of Medicine. (n.d.). TSH (thyroid-stimulating hormone) test: Medlineplus medical test. MedlinePlus.
 52. National Library of Medicine. (2022, September 26). Physiology, luteinizing hormone - StatPearls - NCBI Bookshelf.
 53. Meachem, S. J., Nieschlag, E., & Simoni, M. (2001). Inhibin B in male reproduction: pathophysiology and clinical relevance. *European journal of endocrinology*, 145(5), 561–571.
 54. professional, C. C. medical. (n.d.). Follicle-stimulating hormone (FSH): What it is & function. Cleveland Clinic.
 55. National Library of Medicine. (2022a, July 25). Physiology, prolactin - statpearls - NCBI bookshelf.
 56. Insulin-Like Growth Factor - Health Encyclopedia - University of Rochester Medical Center. (n.d.).
 57. Professional, C. C. M. (n.d.). T4 (Thyroxine) Test. Cleveland Clinic.
 58. Bailey, K. R., Yazdi, T., Masharani, U., Tyrrell, W. B., Butch, A. W., & Schaufele, F. (2016). Advantages and Limitations of Androgen Receptor-Based Methods for Detecting Anabolic Androgenic Steroid Abuse as Performance Enhancing Drugs. *PLOS ONE*, 11(3), e0151860.
 59. Hedström, M., Sjöberg, K., Brosjö, E., Aström, K., Sjöberg, H., & Dalén, N. (2002). Positive effects of anabolic steroids, vitamin D and calcium on muscle mass, bone mineral density and clinical function after a hip fracture: A randomised study of 63 women. *The Journal of Bone and Joint Surgery*.
 60. Pawlikowski, B., Vogler, T.O., Gadek, K. and Olwin, B.B. (2017), Regulation of skeletal muscle stem cells by fibroblast growth factors. *Dev. Dyn.*, 246: 359-367.
 61. Husam Ghanim and others, Effect of Testosterone on FGF2, MRF4, and Myostatin in Hypogonadotropic Hypogonadism: Relevance to Muscle Growth, *The Journal of Clinical Endocrinology & Metabolism*, Volume 104, Issue 6, June 2019, Pages 2094–2102
 62. Bhasin, S., Woodhouse, L. J., & Storer, T. W. (2001). HORMONES AND SPORT Proof of the effect of testosterone on skeletal muscle. Division of

- Endocrinology, Metabolism, and Molecular Medicine, Charles R Drew University of Medicine and Science.
63. Zhang, Y., & Parker, M. A. (1985). Regulation of prostatic steroid binding protein mRNAs by testosterone. *Molecular and Cellular Endocrinology*, 43(2–3), 151–154.
 64. Bates, P. C., Chew, L. F., & Millward, D. J. (1987). Effects of the anabolic steroid stanozolol on growth and protein metabolism in the rat, *Journal of Endocrinology*, 114(3), 373–381. Retrieved Jun 5, 2023
 65. Adaptation of human skeletal muscle to training and anabolic steroids | Health & Environmental Research Online (HERO) | US EPA. (n.d.).
 66. Demling, R. H., & DeSanti, L. (2003). Oxandrolone induced lean mass gain during recovery from severe burns is maintained after discontinuation of the anabolic steroid. *Burns*, 29(8), 793–797.
 67. Guo, W., Bachman, E., Li, M., Roy, C. N., Blusztajn, J. S., Wong, S. K., Chan, S. L., Serra, C., Jasuja, R., Travison, T. G., Muckenthaler, M. U., Nemeth, E., & Bhasin, S. (2013). Testosterone administration inhibits hepcidin transcription and is associated with increased iron incorporation into red blood cells. *Aging Cell*, 12(2), 280–291.
 68. Kuhn, V., Diederich, L., Keller, T. S., Kramer, C., Lückstädt, W., Panknin, C., Suvorava, T., Isakson, B. E., Kelm, M., & Cortese-Krott, M. M. (2017). Red Blood Cell Function and Dysfunction: Redox Regulation, Nitric Oxide Metabolism, Anemia. *Antioxidants & Redox Signaling*, 26(13), 718–742.
 69. Jones, I., Togashi, R., Hatch, G. F. R., Weber, A. E., & Vangsness, C. T. (2018). Anabolic steroids and tendons: A review of their mechanical, structural, and biologic effects. *Journal of Orthopaedic Research*, 36(11), 2830–2841.